

THE EFFECT OF PRE-BOND CONTAMINATION WITH FINGERPRINT AND AGEING ON THE FRACTURE TOUGHNESS OF COMPOSITE BONDED JOINTS*

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Abstract

The effect of the pre-bond contamination with fingerprint, both during the production and the application of adhesively bonded patch repairs on composite aircraft parts, and the combined effect of fingerprint and hygrothermal ageing on the fracture toughness of carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) bonded joints are experimentally investigated. To this end, mode I and mode II fracture toughness tests were conducted on fingerprint contamination coupons and mode II fracture toughness tests on contaminated/aged coupons. The artificial fingerprint was applied in the middle of the adherent's surface in the size of a human fingerprint. The fingerprints consisted of an artificial hand perspiration solution, for the production scenario, and of Skydrol hydraulic-oil, for the repair scenario. Three levels of contamination with fingerprint were considered for each scenario. The hygrothermal ageing conditions applied until saturation were 70°C/85% RH. For the production scenario, the negative effect of the fingerprint contamination on the fracture toughness was designated. The reduction was even greater for the contaminated/aged samples compared to the uncontaminated joints. For the repair scenario, the results were contradictory since G_{IC} fracture toughness increased with increasing the level of contamination, while G_{IIC} fracture toughness deteriorated as a result of the increasing level of contamination. The combined fingerprint contamination and hygrothermal ageing for the repair scenario led to even greater reduction of the G_{IIC} fracture toughness compared to the reference joints.

Keywords CFRP adhesive bonds; fingerprint contamination; fracture toughness; hygrothermal ageing.

1. Introduction

Besides the attractive advantages that adhesive bonding technology offers (da Silva *et al.*, 2011) its full adoption in the primary aircraft structures is currently inhibited due to the lack of effective non-destructive inspection techniques and the durability issues of the adhesive bonded joints (Pantelakis and Tserpes, 2014). It is of utmost importance that the sensitivity of the bondline integrity to environmental factors is taken into account during either the production or the repair of bonded joints appearing in aeronautical applications. In Markatos *et al.*, 2013, a variety of possibly harmful factors are presented and experimentally investigated, revealing the detrimental effect of contaminants, such as release agent contamination, moisture uptake or thermal degradation, on the mechanical performance of composite bonded joints.

The contamination of the bonded surfaces prior to bonding by fingerprints is a commonly encountered scenario as a result of inadequate or incomplete cleaning of the bonding surfaces or inappropriate handling during the fabrication and maintenance stages (Salvato *et al.*, 2017; Creemers *et al.*, 2016). In particular, fingerprint contamination may result from fingerprints that are either clean containing mainly the natural elements of a human fingerprint e.g. sodium chloride, or impure with chemicals generated by adjacent manufacturing or processing operations such as hydraulic oils. Fingerprint contamination is reported to lead to the formation of thin contaminant films that may or may not be uniformly deposited on the bonding surfaces affecting the adhesion quality (Gause, 1989). Since these types of contaminants are invisible, the inspection and quantitative measurement are often complicated and expensive.

Bonded joints are usually implemented in structures which often operate in extreme temperature and moisture conditions. In-service exposure to hygrothermal environment is a critical issue regarding the durability of adhesive bonded joints. The effect of the operating environment in terms of moisture and temperature has been thoroughly investigated (Pitt *et al.*, 2012; Hohnson and Butkus, 1998; Liljedahla *et al.*, 2007) indicating basically a significant loss of the bond strength of joints subjected to ageing. The combination of a pre-bond contamination, e.g. de-icing fluid, of adhesive composite joints and after-bond exposure to hygrothermal ageing has been proven to lead to an even greater loss of mechanical performance (Moutsompegka *et al.*, 2017).

In the present work, the effect of pre-bond contamination with two types of fingerprint, each one encountered during production and repair stages respectively, and the combined effect of fingerprint contamination and hygrothermal ageing on the fracture toughness of CFRP bonded joints is experimentally investigated by means of mode I and mode II fracture toughness tests on contaminated samples and mode II fracture toughness tests on contaminated/aged specimens.

2. Fabrication and pre-bond contamination

2.1 Materials

HexPly M21E/IMA, which was developed specifically for Airbus, is the material used for the preparation of the test panels. Regarding the structural layout, CFRP monolithic structures were manufactured according to Airbus AIPS 03-02-019 standard for CFRP (“Manufacture of monolithic parts with thermoset prepreg materials”). The adherents consisted of 8 unidirectional plies and their layup sequence was $[0_2, \pm 45]_s$ according to AITM 1-0053 (Airbus S.A.S, 2006) standard. A release film of 25 mm length for contaminated samples and 30 mm for contaminated/aged samples was inserted at one end of the sample prior to bonding to obtain an initial delamination. For the adhesive bonding, the film adhesives FM 300K and FM 300-2 from Cytec (0.2 mm thickness) were used for the production and the repair scenario respectively. The sample plates were produced by Aernnova Composites using liquid water based silicon-containing release agent Frekote C-600, in order to obtain smooth surfaces.

2.2 Samples' Preparation

2.2.1 Adherents' preparation

To prepare the clean reference samples from the delivered plates a thorough cleaning procedure was followed to remove part of the release agent and any other soluble contaminations remained from the manufacturing process. This procedure included pre-cleaning of the plates with isopropanol-soaked tissues, two-step slight grinding and final wiping with demineralized water and isopropanol (Moutsompegka *et al.*, 2017). Each step was monitored by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy analyses to measure the amount of release agent on the plate surface. After the cleaning steps, the sample plates were wiped with methyl ethyl ketone (MEK)-soaked tissues prior to contamination and adhesive bonding.

2.2.2 Contamination and bonding of the adherents

Samples for production scenario with fingerprint contamination were prepared using a standardized salty fingerprint solution (artificial hand perspiration solution) according to DIN ISO 9022-12 (ISO, 2012). This solution contains sodium chloride, urea, ammonium chloride, lactic acid, acetic acid, pyruvic acid and butyric acid in demineralized water. Samples were prepared by applying this solution with the size of a fingerprint to the samples. Different degrees of contamination were achieved by using different dilutions (with demineralized water) of the FP solution (vol %): low contamination level 10% (P-FP-1), medium level 50% (P-FP-2) and high contamination level of pure FP solution (P-FP-3). The samples with each FP concentration were controlled by XPS measurements. Based on these measurements (Table I), each contamination level consists of the following concentrations of Na and Cl (main elements) on the CFRP surfaces:

Table I. XPS-results of CFRP samples with different fingerprint solution concentrations.

Scenario	Na (at%)	Cl (at%)
P-FP-1	0.2 ± 0.1	0.5 ± 0.3
P-FP-2	0.5 ± 0.1	0.9 ± 0.0
P-FP-3	0.7 ± 0.1	1.1 ± 0.2

For the repair scenario fingerprints containing Skydrol 500B-4 hydraulic-oil from Eastman were applied on the surfaces using a plastic finger. It was diluted in heptane to obtain solutions with the following concentrations in vol%: low level 20% (R-FP-1), medium level 50% (R-FP-2) and high level of contamination 100% (R-FP-3). Since Skydrol has the tendency to spread over the surface, no clear fingerprints can be observed after a while. XPS measurements could not be conducted for this contamination scenario since the oil evaporates in the vacuum chamber.

For the bonding of the CFRP plates, the adhesive for the production and repair scenarios was cured in an autoclave cycle in accordance with the materials' data sheet specifications. Fig. 1 shows the preparation of the samples for bonding in the autoclave. Finally, the sample plates were cut to the final specimen dimensions specified by the standards of the mechanical tests. Cutting was performed dry (diamond cutting) to prevent any contamination of the cleaned surfaces. After cutting, the surfaces were cleaned again with IPA soaked tissues.

Fig. 1. Preparation of samples for bonding in the autoclave.

3. Experimental Procedure

In order to evaluate the effect of the FP contamination on the mechanical behavior of the adhesive composite joint, mode I and mode II fracture toughness tests were conducted on FP contaminated joints while the effect of the combined FP contamination and after-bond hygrothermal ageing was studied conducting hygrothermal ageing on already FP contaminated samples and subsequent mode II tests on the aged joints.

3.1 Mode-I fracture toughness test

Mode I fracture toughness tests were conducted on double cantilever beam (DCB) specimens (Fig. 2) according to AITM 1-0053 (Airbus S.A.S, 2006) standard using a Tinius Olsen H5KT universal testing machine with a load cell of 5 KN at ambient conditions (25°C/55%RH) under constant displacement control. In order to minimize unstable crack propagation at high crosshead rates, the rate was kept constant at 5 mm/min. The samples were preloaded until an initial crack length of 10 to 15 mm from the end of the insert film was achieved. The pre-cracked specimens were then loaded continuously by opening forces until a total propagated crack length of 100 mm was reached. After that, the test was stopped and the specimen was unloaded. A traveling microscope was used to facilitate the visual measurement of the crack length.

Fig. 2. Schematic representation of the DCB specimen

The AITM 1-0053 specification defines the area method to determine the mode I fracture toughness energy G_{IC} of CFRP bonded joints:

$$G_{IC} = \frac{A}{\alpha \times w} \times 10^6 \quad (\text{J/m}^2) \quad (1)$$

where:

A is the energy to achieve the total propagated crack length (the area enclosed between the loading and unloading curves) (J)

α is the propagated crack length ($\alpha = a_{final} - a_{initial}$) (mm)

w is the specimen width (mm)

After the tests the failure surfaces were examined in order to accurately access the cause of the failure. The characterization of the failure mode of the CFRP bonded joints was conducted according to ASTM D5573 (ASTM International, 2005) standard. The three basic failure modes are cohesive, adhesive and fracture of the adherent.

3.2 Mode-II fracture toughness test

Since up to now there is no standardized mechanical test to measure the fracture toughness energy of bonded joints under pure mode II loading, the end notched flexure (ENF) test was used as the most convenient mode II fracture toughness test (Moutsompegka *et al.*, 2017). Fig. 3 illustrates a schematic representation of the ENF test.

A pre-cracked specimen is loaded in a three-point bending fixture until the crack propagation onset. Mode II tests were conducted according to the AITM 1-0006 (Airbus S.A.S, 1994) standard under a constant displacement rate of 1 mm/min using an MTS universal testing machine with a load capacity of 100 kN. The test specimens were cut from the residual part of mode I specimens so that a pre-crack of 35 mm was achieved. In order to facilitate the optical observation of the crack tip and the detection of the crack propagation onset, a digital microscope was used and a thin layer of white ink was applied to the longitudinal side faces of the specimen.

Fig. 3. Schematic representation of the End Notched Flexure specimen

The load applied to the specimen and the crosshead displacement of the test machine were continuously recorded during the test. The mode II fracture toughness G_{IIc} was calculated as follows:

$$G_{IIc} = \frac{9 \times P \times a^2 \times d \times 1000}{2 \times w \times (1/4 \times L^3 + 3 \times a^3)} \quad (\text{J/m}^2) \quad (2)$$

where:

- d is the crosshead displacement at crack propagation onset (mm)
- P is the critical load to start the crack propagation (N)
- a is the initial crack length (mm)
- w is the width of the specimen (mm)
- L is the span length (mm)

3.3 Hygrothermal ageing test

Reference and FP contaminated specimens were subjected to hygrothermal ageing using an ESPEC SH-641 environmental chamber in conditions of 70°C/85% RH as determined by the DIN EN 2823 (DIN, 1998) standard for a period of 64-74 days when the saturation point was reached. During the hygrothermal ageing period, the specimens' weight was measured on a weekly basis.

The percentage normalized weight gain $M(t)$ was used as a measure of the absorbed humidity:

$$M(t) = \left(\frac{w_t - w_0}{w_0} \right) \times 100 \quad (3)$$

where:

- w_0 is the initial weight (g)
- w_t is the weight at exposure time t (g)

Fick's law was used to define equilibrium conditions in composite materials. The diffusion coefficient D of water is derived from the slope of the linear part of $M(t)$ curve as

$$D = \pi \times \left(\frac{h}{4 \times M_{\infty}} \right)^2 \times S^2 \quad \left(\frac{\text{mm}^2}{\text{s}} \right) \quad (4)$$

where:

M_{∞}	is the water uptake at saturation	(%)
h	is the specimen thickness	(mm)
S	is the slope of the $M(t)$ curve	$(1/\text{s}^{0.5})$

After the hygrothermal ageing, the specimens were stored in sealed containers and tested in mode II loading conditions within 72 hours. The specimens were placed inside the environmental chamber with an embedded pre-crack, which was created a priori through mode I tests conducted according to the AITM 1-006 (Airbus S.A.S, 1994) standard.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Effect of fingerprint contamination

4.1.1 Mode I fracture toughness

The experimental load-displacement curves of the mode I tests of the different P-FP concentration levels, including the reference one, are plotted in Fig. 4. It is observed that all specimens exhibited an unstable crack growth.

Fig. 4. Experimental mode I load-displacement curves of a) P-REF, b) P-FP-1, c) P-FP-2 and d) P-FP-3 specimens.

The G_{IC} values of the specimens are presented in Fig. 5. The results indicate a negative effect of FP as G_{IC} is reduced as the level of contamination increases. Specifically, for P-FP-1 the average G_{IC} value is the same as the reference one indicating that the FP concentration of the low contamination level does not affect the G_{IC} fracture toughness. For P-FP-2 the average G_{IC} starts to reduce by the percentage of 8%, while for the high contamination level P-FP-3 the G_{IC} fracture toughness of the joints degrades significantly by 39% designating the detrimental effect of FP contamination on the bond performance.

Fig. 5. Average G_{IC} values comparison for the production scenario.

After the mode I tests, the fracture surfaces of the samples were studied and characterized determining the main failure mode. For the P-FP scenario, it was observed that the main and the only failure mode observed on the surfaces was adhesive fiber tear at a percentage of 100% regardless of the contamination level. Fig. 6 shows representative fracture surfaces failed adhesively.

Fig. 6. Representative fracture surfaces of the production scenario samples loaded in mode I.

For the R-FP contamination scenario, the experimental load-displacement curves of the mode I tests including the reference one, are illustrated in Fig. 7. The average G_{IC} values of the different R-FP contamination scenarios are compared at the histogram of Fig. 8. Contrary to the P-FP category, for the R-FP scenario the contamination with the Skydrol fingerprint seems to have a positive effect on the mechanical performance of the joint. Specifically, for R-FP-1 and R-FP-2 the average G_{IC} values showed a reduction of 40% and 26% respectively compared to the reference category. It is observed that R-FP contamination causes a reduction in the mode I fracture toughness of the joint, but an increase in the contamination level leads to a smaller reduction on the G_{IC} . This trend keeps appearing at the high contamination level R-FP-3, where G_{IC} not only was increased compared to the low and medium contamination level but it presented a G_{IC} which is higher than the reference category by 17%.

Fig. 7. Experimental mode I load-displacement curves of a) R-REF, b) R-FP-1, c) R-FP-2 and d) R-FP-3 specimens.

Fig. 8. Average G_{IC} values comparison for the repair scenario.

In Fig. 9, photos of the fracture surfaces, showing the main failure modes observed in the mode I tested R-FP specimens, are illustrated and in Fig. 10, the percentages of the different failure modes are compared for the different sample sets. In the reference samples, a mixed-mode failure was observed (Fig. 10a) with the dominant failure being the fiber-tear failure at a percentage of 50%, while the cohesive failure was observed at 35% of the surface area and the adhesive failure at 15%. In the R-FP-1 samples (Fig. 10b), the cohesive failure was slightly reduced to 28%, while a larger surface failed presenting fiber-tear mode (72%), indicating a reduction in bond strength also presented in the G_{IC} value reduction.

For the R-FP-2 scenario, the fiber-tear mode remains the main failure mode with a proportion of 60%, which is greater compared to the R-REF scenario still revealing a negative effect of the R-FP contamination. However, it is observed that the cohesive failure increased to 38% compared with the R-FP-1 samples, endorsing the

greater G_{IC} for the R-FP-2 series compared to the R-FP-1. This can be explained by the fact that cohesive failure requires the greatest amount of energy to develop compared to adhesive failure or fiber-tear failure, thus presenting an increase in the G_{IC} fracture toughness energy.

Finally, the cohesive failure is increased further for the R-FP-3 scenario reaching 49%, while fiber-tear failure was observed at a percentage of 46% compared to the R-REF category. The small adhesive failure percentages observed may indicate that the fingerprint contamination does not affect the interface between the adherent and the adhesive, while the sizable fiber-tear failure percentages may lead to the conclusion that CFRP adherent is highly influenced by the contaminant.

Fig. 9. Representative fracture surfaces of the a) R-REF, b) R-FP-1, c) R-FP-2, d) R-FP-3 specimens loaded in mode I.

Fig. 10. Average percentages of the failure modes presented in the mode I tested R-FP joints.

4.1.2 Mode II fracture toughness

The experimental load-displacement curves of the aged and unaged P-FP ENF? specimens are presented in Fig. 11. The curves of the unaged specimens show an initial linear behavior of the specimens followed by the region where matrix cracking started to accumulate at the adherents until macroscale failure of the outer layers of the adherents as a result of compression. The crack initiation was not followed by a rapid load drop as a result of the small adhesive thickness compared to the adherent’s thickness.

Fig. 11. Experimental Mode-II load-displacement curves of a) P-REF, b) P-FP-1, c) P-FP-2 and d) P-FP-3 aged and unaged specimens.

The G_{IIc} values of the unaged and aged P-FP specimens are presented in Fig. 12. As in mode I, the impact of P-FP on the mode II fracture toughness of the unaged specimens is detrimental. The increase of contamination level causes a further reduction of G_{IIc} . Specifically, for P-FP-1, a reduction of 62% is observed regarding the reference values, for P-FP-2 the corresponding value is 78%, while for P-FP-3 the reduction reaches 69%.

Fig. 12. Average G_{IIc} values comparison of the P-FP scenario.

For the R-FP series, the experimental load-displacement curves of the aged and unaged specimens are illustrated in Fig. 13, while the comparison of the average G_{IIc} values is presented in

Fig. 14. It is observed that R-FP contamination reduces drastically the mode II fracture toughness of the joints. Specifically, F-FP-1 and R-FP-2 contamination levels cause a reduction of approximately 60%, while R-FP-3 reduces further the G_{IIc} to a percentage of 82% compared to the R-REF category. This reduction in bond strength

could be attributed to the fact that the contamination of the adherents with FP leads to poor adhesion between the adhesive and the adherent forming kissing bonds.

Fig. 13. Experimental Mode-II load-displacement curves of a) R-REF, b) R-FP-1, c) R-FP-2 and d) R-FP-3 aged and unaged specimen.

Fig. 14. Average G_{IIC} values comparison of the R-FP scenario.

4.2 Combined effect of FP contamination

4.2.1 Moisture absorption

Fig. 15 plots $M(t)$ with regard to exposure time for the different scenarios. The diffusion parameters derived using Equations (3) and (4) for the different cases are listed in Table 2. The final water uptake was between 0.52% and 0.60%, similar for all cases.

D can be used to compare the diffusion rate within the material system. In R- FP-2 and R-FP-3contamination levels, D is reduced compared to the D value of the reference category, indicating an increase in the joint's resistance to moisture absorption due to the presence of Skydrol based fingerprint. Skydrol reacts with water producing phosphoric acid which can etch the CFRP (Markatos *et al.*, 2013)

Fig. 15. Variation of normalized weight gain $M(t)$ with regard to exposure time t for a) production scenario and b) repair scenario.

Table 2. Moisture diffusion parameters.

Scenario	M_{∞} (%)	D (mm^2/s) $\times 10^{-6}$
P-A-REF	0.57	0.3441
P-A-FP-1	0.53	0.3965
P-A-FP-2	0.63	0.3510
P-A-FP-3	0.55	0.3869
R-A-REF	0.56	0.3922
R-A-FP-1	0.52	0.3915
R-A-FP-2	0.56	0.3811
R-A-FP-3	0.60	0.3305

4.2.2 Mode II fracture toughness

Both for the P-FP and the R-FP category, the comparison of experimental load-displacement curves of the reference aged and unaged samples (Fig. 11, Fig. 13) shows no significant influence of hygrothermal ageing under the specified temperature and moisture conditions. However, the G_{IIc} values of the aged samples are drastically reduced for all contamination levels.

Specifically, regarding the P-FP series, the reduction of the G_{IIc} for the aged reference samples was decreased by 75% compared to the unaged reference category. For the A-R-FP-1 samples, the decrease was 68%, which is higher than the decrease caused solely by the fingerprint contaminant revealing that the combined contamination and ageing is more detrimental for the mode II fracture toughness of the joints. Similarly, the R-A-FP-2 and R-A-FP-3 series presented a decreased G_{IIc} by 80% and 84% respectively compared to the unaged reference category.

The drastic reduction of the G_{IIc} can be attributed to the fact that the crack propagation onset is observed at the specimen side where the moisture concentration is higher. Additionally, the crack propagation occurred near the adhesive region and diffusion through the adhesive is regarded as the primary access route for moisture to enter the joint (Bowditch, 1996).

5. Conclusions

The aim of the present work was to experimentally investigate the effect of pre-bond contamination with fingerprint and the combined effect of fingerprint contamination and hygrothermal ageing on the fracture toughness of CFRP bonded joints. To this end, mode I and mode II fracture toughness tests were conducted on

contaminated specimens and mode II fracture toughness tests on contaminated/aged specimens. Three different levels of fingerprint contamination were considered for each production and repair stage. For the production stage, the fingerprint contamination consisted of an artificial hand perspiration solution (P-FP), while for the repair scenario the fingerprint consisted of Skydrol hydraulic oil (R-FP). The hygrothermal ageing conditions applied until saturation are 70°C/85% RH. From the experimental results the following conclusions can be drawn:

- The increase of the P-FP contamination concentration leads to an increased reduction of the mode I fracture toughness of the joint.
- Although R-FP contamination degrades the mode I fracture toughness of the joint, it was observed that the increase of contamination level led to a smaller decrease in the G_{IC} . This phenomenon was also endorsed by the failure mode presented in the samples, where an increasing cohesive failure mode was observed.
- Pre-bond contamination with fingerprint significantly degrades the mode I and mode II fracture toughness of the bonded joints. The decrease of G_{IIC} is much larger than the decrease of G_{IC} . The higher the concentration of the fingerprint contamination, the larger the reduction in G_{IC} and G_{IIC} values.
- After-bond hygrothermal ageing significantly degrades the mode II fracture toughness of the composite bonded joints. The decrease is larger for the fingerprint contaminated specimens, which reveals that the combined effect is more severe than the two separate effects.
- The reduction of the G_{IIC} as a result of the hygrothermal ageing was greater for the P-FP series, which was attributed to the fact that the Skydrol contained in the R-FP series reacts with the water from the environmental chamber producing phosphoric acid.

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